

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION OF ADVANCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Polymer composites are finding increasing use in new applications and new geological locations around the world. It has therefore become necessary to determine the predominant mode and rate of degradation in these new environments so appropriate protective measures may be applied to maximise the service life of polymer components. Glass-fibre reinforced epoxy composites have been exposed to collect strength degradation data and provide an understanding of the degradation mechanisms that affect polymer composites in Southern Africa. Specimens exposed in a warm humid climate experienced the worst degradation. Epoxy 1 experienced complete fibre exposure after 43 weeks of exposure. Epoxy 2 experienced pitting and surface cracks after 20 weeks of exposure. The synergistic effect of UV radiation and moisture appears to be the most detrimental to the laminates.

Keywords: durability, degradation, environment, testing

INTRODUCTION

Due to increasing use of polymer composites in structural applications, it is becoming increasingly important to determine the rate of degradation of the material in the service environment. The determination of the degradation rates and modes are generally undertaken by real-time exposure in the end-use environment and testing the material after accelerated weathering in an environmental chamber. Accelerated weathering techniques are generally used on a comparative basis to compare materials. It is at present difficult to correlate accelerated test results with real-time exposure [1]. The most reliable method of testing the durability of the laminates is by exposure to the service environment. Due to advances in polymers, such testing may not be feasible, as test durations tend to span a period of years.

Dexter [2] has undertaken exposure tests in America, Europe and New Zealand. The tests performed were on ground-based and in-flight specimens. From the tests, it appears that the unprotected specimens were most affected by exposure. Dexter has reported the data collected from the tests and quantified the strength loss of the materials tested. Chester and Baker [3] have tested polymer composites at tropical sites in Australia and Malaysia. Unprotected laminates were found to rapidly degrade on exposure to UV radiation. Damaged and simple repairs to laminates were tested and found to have excellent durability. Yoosefinejad and Hogg [4] have conducted tests on panels that have been exposed to the UK environment, in a particular case, 20 years. The panels did not support any structural loads for a significant period in service. The deterioration in strength has been attributed primarily to weathering. Cracks were found in the gel coat when examined. Fukuda [5] reported no significant change in bending strength and modulus of specimens exposed in Japan after three years of exposure although the surface coating sustained damage during the exposure. The literature examined [2-5] above does not make a detail study into the modes of degradation incurred or attempt to relate the damage to environmental variables.

There is at present little known information on the performance of polymer composites in the Southern African environment. There is therefore a lack of data for the design and maintenance of composite components and structures. Data presently used for polymer composites is limited to data collected from tests in Europe and America. Composite structures may therefore be over-designed with respect to durability for use in Southern Africa inhibiting product optimisation on cost.

Epoxy composite specimens have been manufactured and mounted at different locations within Southern Africa. Unprotected specimens were mounted for maximum solar exposure to establish the worst-case effect of the environment. The specimens were tested periodically to determine the change in bulk material properties and predominant mode of degradation.

Knowing the degradation rate, the service life of the component can be determined based on when strength has decreased to a critical limit such that the probability of failure is high. Knowing the causes and the rate of the degradation, the effectiveness of protective measure may be determined.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

Test specimens were cut from laminated sheets fabricated using woven glass fibre and an epoxy matrix. Two glass weaves with two corresponding matrices were fabricated.

Epoxy 1 was obtained in prepreg form. It is a toughened epoxy resin, of aerospace grade, that may be used for structural applications requiring high strength, stiffness and damage tolerance. Epoxy 2 was obtained as a cold curing resin used for aerospace and industrial composites, tooling and aircraft repairs.

Woven 8-harness satin-weave E-glass was supplied in the prepreg form with epoxy 1. This woven fabric of 7581 glass had an areal weight of 300g/m². Laminates fabricated by wet lay-up using epoxy 2 were reinforced using woven 2×2 twill weave E-glass. The reinforcing 1102 glass used had an areal weight of 290g/m².

Processing

Epoxy 1 specimens were cut from laminated sheets comprising of nine layers of prepreg, processed as per manufacturers instructions. The processing consisted of two stages, impregnation and cure, as is common for processing prepreg material.

Epoxy 2 laminates were fabricated using ten layers of 2×2 twill-weave glass. A fibre resin ratio (mass) 50:50 was obtained. Wet lay-up using a brush was used, with rolling after each layer. To keep the resin content constant, it was best to measure out the amount of resin required per layer, and make sure that only the resin required per layer is used.

Lay-up began with a coat of resin being applied to the mould surface. A layer of glass was laid upon the resin and properly wetted out from above with resin. The second layer of glass was laid upon the first and roller compacted. Resin from the layer beneath was forced to the top. Resin was added to the top surface to ensure proper wetting before the next layer of glass was placed. This process of adding a layer of glass, rolling down and wetting out was continued until all ten layers were used. After the last layer, the laminate was compacted by roller a final time to ensure even distribution of resin. The laminates were left to cure overnight at ambient temperature with a 60°C, 16 hour post-cure completed the following day. Test specimens were cut using a band saw to dimensions of 150×50mm.

Exposure set-up

Each exposure frame is approximately 1m² in area and holds 108 specimens. The specimens are mounted on a stainless steel sheet fixed to a mild steel chassis and masked with a stainless cover containing cut-outs off approximately 130×40mm through which the specimens receive the exposure. The exposure frames are set-up as latitude racks, i.e. the exposed specimens are inclined to the horizontal at an angle corresponding to the latitude of the test region. In South Africa the racks are set

up at 30°, facing North, at all test sites to keep the angle uniform although the latitude of the test sites vary with a range of 12 degrees within the country. Latitude racks are used to maximise the total solar irradiance to which the specimens are exposed [6]. They thus represent the worst-case scenario or maximum solar radiation that composite components are exposed to in Southern Africa.

Sampling

Sampling has been set at six monthly intervals. The samples are weighed and the mass recorded before any test are performed on the specimen. The change in mass can therefore be determined.

Environment

Six test sites were identified for outdoor exposure testing as illustrated in Figure 1. The six test sites were chosen to represent the diverse climates experienced in Southern Africa. The sites populated in 2002 were Durban, Pretoria and Northern Karoo. Test sites were chosen as they represented the most likely areas that aircraft with composite components would be grounded, different climatic conditions and convenience in monitoring the exposed specimens. Tests were carried out on specimens at sites populated in 2002, as exposure has only recently been initiated at the remaining sites.

Pretoria (A), on the highveld, experiences moderate rain and is cool with frost. The northern Karoo (B) experiences a dry climate with less than 100mm rain, typical of a desert environment. Extreme temperatures are experienced, i.e. high in summer and low in winter. Durban (C) located on the eastern coast of South Africa experiences a wet and humid climate. Cradock (D) in the eastern Karoo has an extreme climate which is predominantly cold and wet. Overberg (E) at the southern Cape has a moderate climate with rainfall through-out the year. Komatidraai (F) on the low-lying mountain bushveld is characterised by high temperature and high humidity.

During the period of exposure, the seasons passed from autumn to spring. Ambient temperatures ranged from 25°C to 16°C with a cumulative rainfall of 415mm. Global radiation ranged from 2200kJ/m² to 1200kJ/m². Durban was the warmest of the three locations during the winter months. Pretoria recorded the highest radiation during the exposure period with intensity ranging from 3000kJ/m² to 1700kJ/m².

☆ exposure locations

Figure 1 – Environmental exposure sites in South Africa

RESULTS

Visual

All samples were inspected visually to determine macroscopic changes to the exposed surface. Fibres were visible on both epoxy laminates to different degrees. The term “fibre exposure” will be used to describe fibres being visible below the surface of the laminate while the term “fibre prominence” will be used to describe the case where fibres protrude above the surface of the laminate. Epoxy 1 became progressively darker in colour before fibres were exposed. Fibre prominence subsequently began imparting a white haze to the surface. The fibre prominence occurred at periodic intervals on the exposed surface suggesting that the epoxy was wearing uniformly over the surface. Figure 2 illustrates the fibre prominence on the surface of epoxy 1 with the attached scale in millimetres. Epoxy 2, which was originally white, began to change yellow in colour. The yellowing increased with time. Fibre exposure was noticed with the fibre becoming visible in areas where the epoxy had cracked and broken away from the laminate. After 43 weeks, fibres were prominent on epoxy 1 laminates whereas fibre exposure was observed on laminates fabricated from epoxy 2.

Figure 2 - Fibre prominence on epoxy 1 after 43 weeks exposure at 5× magnification

Optical Microscopy

The specimens at the coast appear to have been most affected by exposure to the environment. Examination at higher magnification revealed fibre prominence after 10 weeks exposure of epoxy 1. The resin appeared smooth at the surface. When viewed under magnification of 10×, exposed fibres were clearly visible with a repeat pattern of the weave. Fibres perpendicular to visible fibres were exposed in certain areas of the laminate, indicating the depth of resin loss, i.e. one half the depth of the first layer of fibres after 43 weeks exposure. After 20 weeks of exposure cracks appeared to have formed on the surface of the laminate. Closer examination of the surface of the laminate of epoxy 2, at 100× magnification, reveals the cracked surface of the resin after 10 weeks exposure. Regular circular/elliptical shaped holes were observed on the surface with the cracks originating from the circumference of the holes. Figure 3 shows the surface of epoxy 2 at 100× magnification after 20 weeks exposure. Fibre exposure was observed in areas of the laminate where the surface resin had been worn and broken away after 43 weeks of exposure.

Figure 3 - Holes on the surface of epoxy 2 after 20 weeks exposure at 100× magnification

SEM

SEM examination was done on the cross-section of the laminates to determine the depth of damage from the exposed surface. All SEM examinations were done on samples exposed for a duration of 20 weeks. Epoxy 1 showed no visible signs of surface cracks. The resin at the surface showed no signs of damage. Examination the epoxy 2 laminate revealed the average depth of surface cracks to be approximately 20 μ m. Crack propagation from surface cracks can also be observed as in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Cross-sectional view of epoxy 2 after 20 weeks exposure at 600× magnification

Compression tests

Compression testing was performed to quantify the change in strength of the exposed specimen after 10 weeks of exposure. From the data, it appears that the standard deviation of the exposed specimens is consistently lower than that for the unexposed specimens. The reason may be due to variation in

batch processing while during weathering all specimens experience the same conditions, hence the lower standard deviation.

The standard deviation of the average compressive strength epoxy 2 specimens is approximately 12%. For epoxy 2, strengthening may have occurred due to average strengths of specimens at all locations having higher averages than the unexposed specimens. The increase in strength cannot be quantified as the averages occur within the standard deviation of the unexposed specimens tested. The statistics of the strength data appear in Table 1 below. Figure 5 compares the average compressive strength of weathered specimens to the average compressive strength of a batch of unexposed specimens.

Location	Maximum [MPa]	Minimum [MPa]	Average [MPa]	Std. Deviation [MPa]
Unexposed specimens	358	407	385	48
Karoo	373	412	392	28
Durban	384	404	391	20
Pretoria	398	420	407	21

Table 1 – Statistics of the epoxy 2 compression strength data after 10 weeks exposure

Figure 5 – Compressive strength of epoxy 2 specimens at three locations after 10 weeks exposure.

The standard deviation of the average compressive strength epoxy 1 specimens is approximately 5%. Analysis of the test results of epoxy 1 shows a decrease in strength for the specimens exposed at Durban, when compared to unexposed specimens. For exposure at Pretoria and Northern Karoo, no significant change in strength was observed. The statistics of the strength data appear in Table 2 below with the data plotted in Figure 6.

Location	Maximum [MPa]	Minimum [MPa]	Average [MPa]	Std. deviation [MPa]
Unexposed specimens	460	515	494	26
Durban	408	467	446	23
Pretoria	477	510	497	13
Northern Karoo	495	511	505	7

Table 2 – Statistics of the epoxy 1 compressive strength data after 10 weeks exposure.

Figure 6 - Compressive strength of epoxy 1 specimens at three locations after 10 weeks exposure.

DISCUSSION

The sampling period decided upon was approximately 6 months. The first set of samples was removed after approximately 3 months (10 weeks) to verify no significant degradation had occurred. Subsequent sampling was done as close as possible to the 6 month interval, resource permitting, with actual exposure duration being recorded.

Epoxy 1 has, after 43 weeks of exposure, been most affected by the environmental exposure when compared to epoxy 2. The laminate colour has changed from light brown to dark brown during the exposure period at all locations. This has been attributed to degradation due to natural UV exposure, similar to yellowing. After 43 weeks of exposure at Durban, fibres were exposed at the surface of the laminate. The fibres formed a regular pattern typical of the weave. Fibres in the rovings at the surface were exposed. Fibres perpendicular to the rovings were visible to a lesser extent due to the satin weave. Dexter [2] also noted fibre prominence and attributed the occurrence to UV degradation. The fibre exposure may also be dependent on precipitation, as specimens exposed in Pretoria, with higher average radiation than Durban, did not have as great a degree of fibre exposure when compared to Durban. Lubin [7] has reported on the relative low resistance of composite materials to rain erosion. Springer *et al* [8] has worked on a mathematical model of rain erosion on composite materials.

Upon increased magnification there appears to be cracking of the surface after 20 weeks exposure, but this could not be verified when viewing the cross-section using an electron microscope. Electron microscopy of the laminate after 20 weeks exposure revealed the resin closest to the surface to be free of cracks and undamaged in the areas at the cross-over of the rovings. These are the “resin rich” regions closest to the surface. Electron microscopy revealed no apparent damage to existing resin on the surface.

Compression test results of specimens at all locations were compared to determine the change in bulk material properties from unexposed material and to compare the relative change of bulk material properties between locations. The specimens exposed in Pretoria and the Northern Karoo had ultimate compressive strengths higher than the unexposed material but within the standard deviation of the unexposed material. A reduction in strength of approximately 10% was recorded for

specimens exposed in Durban. This has been thought to be due to moisture effects as Durban has recorded the most precipitation when compared with the remaining locations.

Mass increase was the maximum for specimens exposed at Durban for the first 20 weeks of exposure. A total mass increase of 0.35% after 10 weeks exposure and 0.26% after 20 weeks exposure was recorded. For accelerated humidity tests, Springer [9] has noted a peak in weight change when the relative humidity is reduced. This however cannot be applied to environmentally exposed specimens although relative humidity may vary with seasons. The weight change due to moisture is difficult to determine as weight loss due to resin increases with time. Resin loss is evident by fibre exposure. The weight change recorded is the overall weight change of the specimens.

Unexposed Epoxy 2 specimens were semitransparent. Upon exposure, the colour of the laminate changed to yellow with the intensity increasing with time at all locations. This has been attributed to degradation by natural UV radiation. Fibre exposure is limited to the areas at which the resin appears to have chipped off. The resin chips predominantly occur in the regions at which the fibre rovings cross and the resulting pits have one edge adjacent to a glass roving. The pits formed have no consistent shape. As the roving in the weave approached the surface, it appears to have hindered the growth of the chips of resin that broke away from the laminate thereby preventing larger pits from forming.

Upon examination under an optical microscope, the fibre rovings at the bottom of the pit could be clearly seen. It appears that the fibre roving may have limited the depth of the pit that formed. At higher magnification, the surface of the laminate has a cracked appearance, with round pits present. These pits are unlikely to be the pits that have been noticed visually as none of the pits observed at higher magnification have the arbitrary shapes that were seen visually. The holes may be due to the leaching of unreacted constituents as described by Vauthier *et al* [10]. Electron microscopy revealed that the average depth of crack is approximately 20 μ m after 20 weeks exposure. The first layer of fibre is on average approximately 70 μ m from the surface, hence the cracks had not propagated to the fibre level after 20 weeks. Larger cracks have been observed to begin within the surface cracks.

The fibre resin ratio is an important parameter that may influence the rate of degradation. On the microscopic level it was observed that due to a 70 μ m layer of resin, on epoxy 2, before the first layer of fibre, cracks at the surface had not reached the fibres after 20 weeks exposure. Epoxy 2 therefore did not display a decrease in compressive strength. The cracked surface may however reduce the fracture toughness of the material by initiating failure in the less degraded material as noted by White and Turnbull. Schoolenberg [11], cited by White and Turnbull, noted that the depth of embrittlement does not necessarily equal the depth of the surface cracks. Epoxy 1, the laminate manufactured from prepreg had a higher fibre resin ratio. The laminate however displayed fibre exposure before observed matrix cracking. The relationship of fibre resin ratio on degradation has been studied [12] by Singh *et al* who found that although laminates with a higher fibre volume ratio had a higher strength when compared to laminates with a low fibre volume ratio, the degradation in strength was faster in higher fibre volume ratio laminates.

The following was observed:

- Mass increase was maximum, 0.19%, for specimens of epoxy 2 exposed at Pretoria after 20 weeks. Specimens exposed at the remaining locations experienced negligible changes in mass.
- The change of colour on laminates does not necessarily imply a change. This has been observed with epoxy 2. Although the laminate yellowed, no decrease in compressive strength was recorded.
- The masked areas of the laminate show no change in appearance when compared unexposed specimens. The masked areas are protected from UV radiation and precipitation.

CONCLUSION

Two types unprotected epoxy laminates have been exposed in the Southern Africa to determine the effect of the environment on the bulk residual material properties. Masked specimens were set-up for maximum natural solar exposure.

Fibre exposure of the first layer of glass was observed on epoxy 1, the specimens with the higher fibre resin ratio, after 10 weeks of exposure. The specimens mounted in the wet environment were found to have a 10% lower compressive strength after 10 weeks of exposure. Surface cracks and circular/elliptical pits were observed on epoxy 2. The average depth of surface cracks was approximately 20µm after 20 weeks exposure. The synergistic effect of UV radiation and moisture appears to be the most detrimental to the laminates.

Damage to unprotected laminates has been incurred after ten weeks of exposure to the environment. Protective measures and proper maintenance are therefore critical to ensure the long term durability of composite components in Southern Africa.

Glass reinforced polyester and vinyl ester laminates are currently exposed at all exposure locations. Determination of degradation will therefore be done on the three most common resins used a matrix for polymer composites. Specimens exposed for 43 weeks are currently being tested. Specimens with gel coats have been produced for accelerated testing which will commence this year.

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